

**THE DEVELOPMENT OF A CULTURE OF HEALTHY LIFESTYLE IN
STUDENT GIRLS THROUGH PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS
AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM**

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Annotation: The content of the article explores the pedagogical conditions for the involvement of female students in physical education and sports, the inclusion and development of the concept of healthy lifestyle culture, the possibilities and effectiveness of physical education and sports, the technological conditions of targeted pedagogical process.

Keywords: healthy lifestyle culture, pedagogical tool, mechanism, motivation, technological process.

Relevance. The current development of modern educational processes in the world is determined by the diversity of its various socio-pedagogical directions and changes, reforms, actions. In order to popularize physical culture and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan in recent years, to promote a healthy lifestyle among the population, to establish priorities for improving the skills and knowledge of the population in the field of physical culture and sports, , the implementation of specific programs in the field of physical culture and sports, which will help to strengthen the health of the population, is very important and relevant [3].

At the current stage of development of society, attention is paid to the healthy lifestyle of students, which is associated with an increase in the health of graduates and their incidence in the process of professional training, followed by a decrease in working capacity [5].

The problem of developing a culture of healthy lifestyle in student girls through physical education and sports is an important issue that needs to be addressed. The state of women's health is an important component of the nation's healthy potential, so maintaining and promoting the health of student girls and developing a culture of healthy lifestyles in them is a priority today. Student girls' health is one of the most pressing socially important issues that need to be addressed in today's society, and to ignore this problem is to lose sight of the future generation.

One of the main conditions for the modernization of society in the process of globalization is the development of the culture of life and the improvement of the social environment [4]

The purpose of the study. The pedagogical conditions for the formation of a healthy lifestyle in students, the identification of factors influencing development, the formation of a healthy lifestyle through physical education and sports, improving health, the development of a culture of healthy living are studied and investigated.

Research methods. Theoretical analysis of the general factors of the development of a culture of healthy life in student girls, the educational value of physical education and sports as a pedagogical tool, and research methods of the literature were used.

Research results and discussion. The concept, content, principles of a healthy lifestyle, in the process of education and upbringing, mechanisms of formation and development of physical culture of a healthy lifestyle in students N.AMeshelkova (2005), T.M.Kravchenko (2004), B.M. Zimasov (2006), I.D.Manchanov (2001), K.Sodikov (2007), O.Jamoliddinova (2010). D.J.Sharipova (2010), A.Raxmonov (2012), S.A.Abitova (2019), N.Sh.Mannapova (2019), Sh.Xankeldiev, A.Abdullaev, Q.Jabborov, R.Hamroqulov , R.Rasulov, A.Hasanov (2010,2011) articles on some problems of the subject, textbooks are the primary literature.

Spelling developments on the pedagogical conditions - conditions, opportunities and effectiveness of the development of a culture of healthy lifestyles of female students through physical education and sports are not enough.

In the available sources, the general aspects of the problem have been studied, and the students, while acknowledging the urgency of the problems of a healthy lifestyle in students, stressed the need to further expand the scope of research.

Study of available scientific sources on the subject Higher education physical culture: including conditions for organizing the pedagogical, technological process of developing a culture of healthy lifestyle through in-class and out-of-class physical education and sports based on observations in the educational process of (women's) education identified:

1. The development of a culture of healthy lifestyle through physical education and sports is described as a social, pedagogical problem, the role and importance of physical culture and sports in the development of a culture of healthy lifestyle and opportunities in higher education.

2. Improving students' knowledge based on behavioral, habits, healthy lifestyles, health care and development skills during the learning process, physical education and sports.

3. Introduction of educational technologies in educational activities, development of the theory of physical education and its harmonization with pedagogical theories of person-centered education.

4. Introduce non-traditional teaching methods in classroom and extracurricular activities aimed at developing a culture of healthy lifestyles among female students.

5. Achieving effectiveness through the use of forms, methods and tools to develop a culture of healthy lifestyles of student girls through physical education and sports.

6. Implementation of mechanisms to ensure the effectiveness of the process of developing a culture of healthy lifestyles in female students through physical education and sports.

7. Criteria for determining the level of students through the development of a culture of healthy lifestyle through physical education and sports, the introduction of its effectiveness in practice.

Physical education is part of a person’s overall culture. In physical culture, man acquires not only his natural existence, but also the culture of humanity, striving to harmonize with himself, the world around him, nature and society.

At the current stage of development of society, the formation of an individual's physical culture is a multifaceted and at the same time integral process, mainly focused on the implementation of physical health programs, physical self-improvement and changes in the level of development of psychophysical qualities and characteristics [5].

Physical education and sports play an important role in the formation of a culture of healthy lifestyle, strengthening human health, increasing its physical and functional capabilities. A person should feel a legitimate and mandatory need for physical activity as part of their lifestyle.

A healthy lifestyle, strengthening health requires regular physical activity and sports. After all, maintaining and strengthening the health of students, the formation of their need for physical education in their physical development is an important task facing educational institutions.

Therefore, there is a need for higher education institutions to conduct in-depth research and studies on the development of a culture of healthy lifestyles among female students through physical education and sports, which determines the relevance of this research.

The institution of higher education is a scientific study of the current practical situation in the culture of healthy lifestyles among female students and shows that it has several distinctive features.

Today, the development of technology, the replacement of work in human activities by technical means has a negative impact on strengthening human health. Also, the modern learning process often leads to a deterioration in student health. The issue of developing a culture of healthy living in students is very important. A healthy lifestyle starts with the family.

It is important to inculcate in students the concept of "healthy lifestyle", "culture of healthy living" and the idea of "healthy living" from an early age.

There are a number of factors that contribute to the deterioration of the health of female students in educational institutions. For example:

- improper adherence to the agenda;
- not to exercise, hygienic requirements;
- connects leisure and leisure time with computer networks, social networks, which are not necessary from mobile devices.

The above-mentioned cases indicate that the student girls spend their time in various idle jobs, have a low culture of health, and are indifferent to their health. Therefore, in the process of physical education of future students of physical culture, in the development of a culture of healthy lifestyle, organization of leisure and leisure, systematic, effective organization of extracurricular activities of national and mass sports clubs in educational institutions plays an important role in shaping and developing a healthy lifestyle . After all, the formation of a motivational attitude to the work of physical education should focus on the acquisition of health as a value direction for students. Therefore, the main goal of physical education and sports in the development of a culture of healthy lifestyle in student girls is to increase the functional, adaptive abilities of the body, the physical development of the individual.

Conclusion. The importance of physical education and sports in the multifaceted process of developing mental, moral and physical qualities, strengthening health, improving work skills, developing a culture of healthy lifestyle and creating a healthy environment in student girls through physical education and sports. Because physical education and sports are effective means of the educational process in the development of a person to mental and moral perfection, physical perfection.

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